

You Are Not Your Mistakes

A Case for Restorative Practice from Psychology to Eternity

by

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1 Introduction

The concepts I will be sharing in this work have had a profound impact on my life, and the changes I have gradually started implementing have helped me live, and love better.

Wherefore by their fruits ye shall know them.

Matthew 7:20

I am not perfect, far from it. I still have a very, very, very, long way to go. However, the practical changes in my thoughts and actions so far are undeniable, and so I decided to share in case this helps anyone like it has helped me. My motivation for writing this is nothing but love.

That said, I welcome thoughtful dialogue and correction. I'm no expert in any of the fields I touch on - just a curious student of love. If you see any points that deserve a bit more nuance or rethinking, I would genuinely appreciate hearing your thoughts.

I hope you enjoy reading!

2 A Brief History of Psychology

To begin, I would like to explore the evolution of Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) over time. I appreciate the detailed work done in the review by Ruggiero et al. [8], which forms the basis for this section. Several analogies will be used to demonstrate key concepts throughout this work, and I hope they make reading more enjoyable. In this section specifically, a chess game will be used to describe an unexpected life situation.

2.1 Setting the Stage: Scholar's Mate

In chess, the Scholar's Mate is one of the first tricks taught to beginners. It is a four-move checkmate (i.e., what is required to win a chess game) played almost exclusively by players who just learned how to move the pieces. Therefore, to make it work, your opponent must not be very good at chess, so I wonder why it is called the scholar's mate. Anyway, I will narrate every move in detail, so do not worry if you have never played a chess game before.

2.1.1 The Four-Move Win Sequence

The game begins with both the white and black players moving their kings' pawns to the center of the board, an opening strategy called the "King's Pawn Opening" (I wonder why). This is a standard line played by beginners and experts alike, so nothing special yet. Most chess opening moves seek to control the center of the board, and the King's Pawn Opening is one of the most common ways to do that.

Figure 1: Scholar's Mate, Move 1

Next, both sides attempt to develop minor pieces, still aiming at controlling the center. For white, it is

crucial that the light squared bishop is moved to the “c4” square, as it is setting up an attack on the black king. Still nothing out of the ordinary.

Figure 2: Scholar's Mate, Move 2

White then makes the bold decision to bring the queen into the attack very early into the game. By moving the queen to the “f3” square, and relying on the support of the bishop previously moved, white threatens checkmate on “f7”, indicated by the red arrow in Figure 3. This is a very aggressive opening move which relies on the ignorance of the player moving the black pieces. I like to call moves like this “hope chess”, i.e risky moves that only pay off if your opponent does not see the threat. For educational purposes, I will assume the player with the black pieces does not want to win, and responds to the threat by moving their queen's pawn to the “d6” square.

Figure 3: Scholar's Mate, Move 3

Finally, white captures the pawn on "f7", and wins by checkmate, as the black king now has no safe moves to make.

Figure 4: Scholar's Mate, Move 4

2.1.2 Scholar's Mate Gone Wrong

Now suppose a slightly similar position to Figure 3 is set up, but this time black sees the threat and defends the pawn by moving their second knight (the horsey piece) to "h6". One of the best things about knights is that they are the only piece in chess that can jump over other pieces, doing so by moving in "L" shaped patterns. In this case, the knight is providing protection to the pawn on "f7" in anticipation of the queen's

attack.

Figure 5: Scholar's Mate Gone Wrong, Move 3

Finally, to set the stage for the next section, we assume that white still captures the pawn hoping for checkmate, only to lose their queen.

Figure 6: Scholar's Mate Gone Wrong, Move 4

The game evaluation bar on the left shows that black is now clearly winning. The game is not over - but this is really hard to come back from, and the player with the white pieces now feels awful for making this error.

2.2 Comparison of Psychological Approaches

To the best of my knowledge, each of the psychological schools of thought presented in this section emerged from a desire to help people feel better. I think that is beautiful. This section details how each school might approach caring for the chess player who just lost their queen.

2.2.1 First Wave: Behaviorism

This school of thought focuses only on observable behavior, and does not consider thoughts or feelings in decision making. For example, if a person avoids dogs due to fear, the behaviorist concludes that exposure to dogs that don't hurt them will help them get over their fear. That is, it is assumed that the person fears dogs because they have been conditioned through previous experiences to associate dogs with danger.

In the context of the chess game, purely behaviorist therapy would attempt to solve the player's problem by making them play several games with Scholar's Mate where they keep losing until they no longer associate that simple trick with winning. Then, once that association is unlearned, they will choose to make a different move that does not result in them losing so early on, and will feel better. In summary, the behaviorist assumes that the only reason why a person would keep playing Scholar's Mate is because it has previously worked. That is, habits are solely motivated by outcomes.

This is a very cause-effect school of thought, and while it seems true for reflexive actions, it often assumes that similar stimuli will yield similar responses across individuals, overlooking differences in internal interpretation or personal meaning. Before proceeding to the next section, can you sit with this for a bit and think of any cases where the player would still keep playing Scholar's Mate even though they keep losing?

2.2.2 Second Wave: Cognitive Revolution

Subsequent schools introduced "thoughts" as the middleman between situations and behaviors. That is, thoughts serve as a buffer between external stimuli and our reactions to them. Two key figures were central to this wave of psychotherapy: Aaron Beck, the founder of Cognitive Therapy (CT) [2], and Albert Ellis, the founder of Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy (REBT) [4].

Cognitive Therapy (CT)

CT focuses on how negative beliefs about the self (e.g., "I suck"), world (e.g., "the world sucks"), and future (e.g., "things will always suck") lead to depression. In the case of the chess analogy, CT explains the player's negative feelings as faulty beliefs about themselves arising from losing their queen. That is, the player isn't sad just because they lost their queen, but rather, they are sad because they think losing

their queen says something about their worth as a person. Therefore, treatment under CT might include affirmations like “Sure, you lost your queen, but that doesn’t say anything about you as a person. You are still a valuable person.” That is, a purely cognitive therapist would focus on changing faulty beliefs, suggesting that it is possible to have positive feelings about the self even in the face of negative situations. In summary, CT says “Yes, failure is bad, but it doesn’t say anything about you as a person”.

Cognitive Therapy is largely considered the foundation of modern Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT).

Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy (REBT)

On the other hand, while REBT also introduces thoughts as a middleman, it focuses on the person’s perception of the situation. In the chess analogy, treatment under REBT would focus on the person’s assessment of what is happening, and could go something like “I agree that losing your queen this early in a game could be considered bad, but it’s not *that* bad. You need to let yourself be okay with losing pieces in a chess game.” That is, REBT focuses on reducing the perception of the severity of the incident. In real life, REBT care focuses on challenging beliefs like “I must be perfect” or “I must live in a mansion to be happy” and helping the client soften their rigid stances.

2.2.3 Second Wave (continued): Constructivism

The constructivist approach suggests that negative thoughts are not just caused by the situation itself, but by the meaning we assign to it - which is shaped by how we see ourselves and our place in the world. That is, the story we tell about ourselves shapes how we interpret events. In the chess analogy, a constructivist therapist might ask why losing your queen feels so painful. For example, if you were a chess grandmaster, losing your queen that way might feel embarrassing, whereas a beginner might shrug it off. Care in this tradition might sound like, “So you lost your queen, and that sucks. But you’re just starting out - you only recently learned how the pieces move. Maybe you can be a bit kinder to yourself.” In summary, constructivism focuses on how identity shapes perception and emotion.

2.2.4 Third Wave: Modern Functional Psychology

Modern Functionalist thought further argues that the stories and values behind our identities serve a function - that is, we are trying to meet some (usually unchanging) goal through the identity we construct for ourselves. Again, returning to the chess analogy, functionalist thought might suggest that your identity as a good chess player could be serving some function (e.g, to get closer to your dad, if your dad really loves chess), which in turn ultimately serves a goal - to be happy. Care in this tradition might sound like: “So you’re sad because you lost your queen, which threatens your identity as a good chess player, which threatens your relationship

with your dad (who loves chess), which threatens your happiness. If being close to your dad makes you happy, what if there were other ways to build that relationship? You could go on a vacation with him, maybe. Do you really have to get close to your dad through chess? Building your identity around being a good chess player doesn't seem to be making you happy anymore, and that's what you really want, right?" (I realize the chess analogy is getting stretched thin at this point, but stay with me - we have just one more school of thought left to cover.)

To summarize the modern functionalist school of thought: our identities and behaviors are understood as tools for meeting deeper (often stable) needs like survival, connection, or happiness. Functionalism focuses less on where your identity came from and more on whether it's still serving its intended purpose - and if not, how to rebuild it in a more effective way.

2.2.5 Adlerian Psychology

Adlerian Psychology shares functionalism's emphasis on purpose, but takes it a step further by insisting that even our goals themselves can change. Adler believed we are not slaves to instinct or fixed drives. Instead, we (often unconsciously) choose goals that organize our behavior. Adlerian psychology prioritizes the goal or outcome we want instead of our identity.

In the chess analogy, Adler might suggest that there are several goals that winning the chess game could achieve. One goal could be to prove your worth to your dad. But another goal could be to win a bet (though, I don't know why you would even try Scholar's Mate if you had money at stake). Yet another goal could be to impress someone you have a crush on who happened to be watching the game. In summary, Adlerian Psychology does not focus on tracing roots back to a fixed purpose but instead takes a future-oriented outlook. In this case, Adler would probably ask you to consider whether winning your crush's attention is a worthy goal - and if not, whether you're ready to shift your goal toward something more fulfilling.

2.3 Please Try Therapy, It Works

Thank you for sticking with me through the chess analogy! I realize that was a lot of information to take in, so I have summarized each psychological approach in Table 1.

School of Thought	Summary
Behaviorist	Play enough games and lose often enough, and you'll stop using bad openings like Scholar's Mate - behavior will adapt through repetition.
Cognitive Therapy (CT)	Losing your queen doesn't mean you're a failure - your self-worth is not tied to the game.
Rational Emotive Behavior Therapy (REBT)	Yes, losing feels bad, but it's not <i>that</i> bad - you can let go of perfectionism and accept setbacks.
Constructivist	You're upset because you see yourself as a good chess player - but you're still learning, and that's okay.
Modern Functionalist	Being good at chess was just a way to connect with your dad - maybe there are better ways to build that connection.
Adlerian	Why play chess to impress your dad? There are other motivations for playing chess that could make games more enjoyable, even when you lose.

Table 1: Summary of Psychological Approaches in the Chess Analogy

Of course, life is more complex than a game of chess, but if you are anything like me, you might've started challenging some of your longstanding beliefs and goals as you read through these concepts. That said, some core beliefs are so deeply ingrained that it is hard to even see them, which is where professional therapy comes in. I remember explaining a situation to my therapist once with so much fire and passion, and his response was, "Wait, Richmond. What if nobody did anything wrong?", with a really calm smile. I was taken aback because I expected him to help me analyze what I (or they) did wrong, but he ended up challenging the foundational belief that was causing me distress in that situation - something I never would've caught on my own.

Essentially, modern CBT-based therapy combines elements of each school of thought, and this is why it is crucial to find a therapist that connects with you. Sometimes that might look like working with a therapist of the same race, gender, neurotype, etc., because there is a chance they are more familiar with your thought patterns and have a better idea of how to help you achieve your goals. In summary, therapy doesn't necessarily "fix" you, it helps you figure out how to make changes that *you* want to make.

If you need further proof, there is strong statistical evidence to support the efficiency of therapy: in a study by Fordham et al., it was found with high confidence that modern CBT is effective across almost any population, condition, and context [5].

2.3.1 Does Therapy Solve Everything?

If you've ever met me in real life, one thing you'll know about me is that I question everything. Sometimes it gets me in trouble, haha. But I wouldn't be who I am if I didn't always ask "why?".

As clear as the evidence is for modern CBT, I still wonder if it completely explains human nature. There are some things we do that seem to defy all logical explanations. For example, I once watched a video of strangers helping pull a man out of his car, which was on fire. Why would they risk their lives to do that? Or if we think about the end of the classic movie *Titanic*, where Jack gave his life so Rose would survive (yes, both of them could have fit on the door, [3] but that's not the point). What would make him even consider doing such a thing?

I think there is something that exists that defies all human logic, and that it is the ultimate motivation for everything that we do. In the book *Sapiens: A Brief History of Humankind* by Yuval Noah Harari [6], he argues early on that religion has been a major driving force for some of mankind's greatest achievements, whether or not God actually exists. In the next section, I will discuss my personal faith system, and connect it to the psychological concepts we have just discussed. I hope to keep it as objective as possible, but I know that is a futile attempt, since I am human, and we have a tendency to project our personal experiences onto things. I just hope that you can read it with an open mind.

3 From Psychology to Theology

Theology is the study of the nature of God and religious belief, derived from the Greek words *theos* (God) and *logia* (study). I am a Christian, so I will primarily draw from Christian Theology. In my faith system, I believe that every man was created in the image of God. Therefore, what better way is there to understand human nature than theology?

Then God said, ‘Let us make man in our image, after our likeness...’

Genesis 1:26

That said, I believe that the concepts I will be discussing have been discussed in all world religions, and I would actually be very curious to read similar arguments from a different faith system. Please share with me if you end up writing one.

Test everything; hold fast what is good.

1 Thessalonians 5:21

I added that quote for my fellow Christians who might be reading this and may have objections to my curiosity in other faith/ethical systems. Let us now dive into the foundations of Christian Theology.

3.1 Free Will or Predestination?

The topic of moral agency is a longstanding debate within the Christian church. Many traditions have differing opinions on this topic, but there are two main camps:

3.1.1 Calvinism

Calvinism emphasizes divine predestination. That is, what we understand to be “free will” is really an illusion, and we are all at the complete mercy of God. One of the key verses used to support this school of thought can be found in the book of Romans:

“For He says to Moses, ‘I will have mercy on whom I have mercy, and I will have compassion on whom I have compassion.’”

Romans 9:15

This appears to suggest that human agency plays little or no role in the things we experience. Furthermore, this red-letter quote (in many Bibles, words spoken by Jesus Himself are written in red letters) sounds pretty clear.

“No one can come to Me unless the Father who sent Me draws him. And I will raise him up on the last day.”

John 6:44

In general, Calvinist theology is the major pillar of Presbyterian churches.

3.1.2 Arminianism

In contrast, Arminianism is a free-will absolutist school of thought that suggests that we all have complete agency over our actions, that is, we have the power to do whatever we want (including rejecting God). Deriving its name from Jacobus Arminius [1], who was trained at the University of Geneva, a Calvinist stronghold, Arminianism has largely become the mainstream theological school of thought, even among traditions that still recognize the need for Grace.

In my first exposure to Christianity, the condition for salvation was presented as a simple choice - say yes to Jesus and you are saved.

For God so loved the world, that He gave His only Son, that whoever believes in Him should not perish but have eternal life. **John 3:16**

This verse is commonly quoted to support that view. That is, all you have to do is to make the *choice* to believe, and you will live eternally. Sounds pretty easy, doesn't it?

3.1.3 Contradicting Views Can Both Be True

I am of the belief that both camps are right. How, you might ask? How is it possible to have free will and still be predestined? If I decide to eat rice for lunch, was I predestined to do so? What if I change my mind and decide to eat beans? Was the act of changing my mind also predestined, or did I exercise my free will to make a different choice?

Clearly, this is not an easy question to answer, so I will use science to demonstrate how it is possible to have two seemingly contradictory viewpoints true at the same time.

Wave-Particle Duality of Matter

Matter is defined as anything that has mass and takes up space. That is, all the “stuff” around us is made up of matter at its fundamental level. In elementary/middle school you might have learned that there are three states of matter: solid, liquid, and gas. Physicists have been able to discover other states of matter that don't fit in any of those three categories, such as “Bose-Einstein Condensate”, but that is beyond the scope of this work. In general, you can think of matter as anything we can perceive to exist with our senses.

While studying the fundamental nature of matter, a baffling discovery was made at the start of the 19th century - Physicist Thomas Young discovered that matter can exist both as “particle” or a “wave” at the quantum level [9]. You can think of a particle as a tangible object, and a wave as a vibration. In essence, he

proved through something called the “Double Slit Experiment” that matter simultaneously exists in both states until it is observed, at which point it is forced to “choose” one. This sounds almost unreal, doesn’t it? To explain further just how baffling this discovery was, I will use an analogy that can help you visualize it better.

Understanding Quantum Mechanics with a Pebble and a Pond

Have you ever dropped a pebble in a pond? When you do, it forms ripples/vibrations like this, right?

Figure 7: Waves/Vibrations in a Pond

One could say that the pebble (particle) has been converted to vibrations in the water (wave). Now, for the baffling part: Thomas Young essentially proved that matter exists in both states **AT THE SAME TIME**. Isn’t that insane to think about? Imagine if you could “rewind” the water waves and turn them back to a pebble and vice versa.

Quantum Mechanics says that all matter is simultaneously the pebble and the water waves *until we look at it*. When our consciousness “observes” it, it is forced to pick whether it wants to be a particle or a wave. This almost makes no sense, yet, it was proven experimentally!!!

The famous “Schrödinger’s Cat” thought experiment also explains the same concept - let’s say you know for a fact that there is a cat in a box, but you don’t know whether it is alive or dead. You can speculate all you want, but you’ll never know for sure until you *look inside the box*. In this example, looking inside the box is what makes you confirm for sure whether the cat is alive (e.g a wave?) or dead (a particle?).

Connecting this to quantum mechanics, Schrödinger suggests that while the box is closed, the cat is both alive and dead at the same time.

I used this example to show that nature itself has taught us that seemingly contradicting views can actually be complementary truths. Using a similar thought process, could it be possible that both Calvinist and Arminian positions do not oppose each other, but rather, point to the same eternal truth?

3.2 Returning to Psychology

Recall that the purpose of including theology in this work at all is to understand human nature, so let us connect these viewpoints back to psychology.

If you think about it, Calvinist theology sounds a lot like modern functionalist psychology. Just as functionalism generally says that all our actions can be connected to some natural/fixed/innate drive, such as our survival instincts, Calvinist theology says that everything we do is predestined. In this case, the concept of free will could fit nicely into Calvinism by saying that what we consider “choices” are just our brains moving us in the direction that we are already hardwired to go. In this setup, therapy can only help us change how we get there, but we are already predestined to end up at some final destination. This popular meme helps us visualize this framework.

Figure 8: The Illusion of Free Will

On the other hand, there is no direct psychological equivalent for Arminianism. Growing up in Nigeria

and hearing John 3:16 quoted all the time, I always wondered what the teachers had to say about those who were born on remote islands. Did they exercise a choice to reject Jesus? How could they reject something they didn't know about? Some teachers said that God would take that into account and be lenient on them. But if that is true, then isn't evangelizing a bad thing? Because when you evangelize, you make them aware of a choice they didn't have, and now it is more likely that they will be doomed to eternal damnation for rejecting Jesus. I don't know about you, but if I woke up from a nap in my cave in the middle of nowhere, and someone told me a middle-eastern guy thousands of miles away died so I could live forever, I would look at you like you were crazy. Isn't it better, then, to just let people be?

3.2.1 Adlerian Psychology as a Bridge

No one does evil willingly.

Socrates

This quote attributed to Socrates says that nobody, regardless of how evil they might appear on the surface, is choosing to do evil willingly. That is, even the worst person imaginable believes that there is some twisted idea of good that can come out of their actions. For example, serial killers that kill for fun are committing evil because they are trying to have "fun", and fun is a good thing. In the serial killer's mind, they believe that the fun they gain from murdering people is more valuable than the pain they might cause, therefore making murder worth it.

In this way, Socrates suggests that every person is really doing what they think will benefit them (or others) in some way, no matter how evil they might seem. This echoes the words of Jesus Christ himself as he was being crucified:

And Jesus said, "Father, forgive them, for they know not what they do."

Luke 23:34

Similarly, Alfred Adler suggested that every action we take is trying to meet a certain goal, and we can change the goal to help change our actions. In this way, Adlerian Psychology acknowledges both Calvinism and Arminianism. While Adler strongly emphasizes our free will to set different goals to achieve happiness (echoing Arminianism), he also recognizes that there is a universal goal that all humans ultimately strive towards (echoing Calvinism). In his work, he called that universal goal "belonging" or "social interest".

I believe the word Adler was looking for is **LOVE**.

For I am sure that neither death nor life, nor angels nor rulers, nor things present nor things to come, nor powers, nor height nor depth, nor anything else in all creation, will be able to separate us from the love of God in Christ Jesus our Lord.

Romans 8:38–39

3.3 Christian Universalism as an Eschatological Framework

Eschatology is a big word that refers to the study of what happens after we die. In Christianity, there are three main eschatological schools of thought:

- Eternal Conscious Torment
- Annihilationism
- Universalism

Eternal Conscious Torment appears to be the mainstream view in Christian spheres, based on my experience church-hopping. However, something in my spirit could never really accept it. That's just me. The idea of being tormented eternally for *finite* crimes seems incompatible with the concept of God's Love and Grace. Annihilationism does not really improve on this either, as it only replaces eternal torment with ceasing to exist. In my opinion, all that does is make things seem a little less worse. Like a human attempt to make God seem a little less bad.

Can a mortal be more righteous than God? Can a man be more pure than his Maker? **Job 4:17**

Instead of trying to reduce the severity of hell, I prefer to focus on understanding God's intentions for us. To do so, I think we need to know His nature, and scripture tells us that God is the very concept of Love itself.

Whoever does not love does not know God, because God is love. **1 John 4:8**

That is, just as water is both wet and makes things wet (one of my friends had this argument with me briefly, haha), God is Love, and also is the reason we are capable of love. This view of God goes beyond earth-centric religion, because if aliens/extra-terrestrials are capable of falling in love, then they are also experiencing God.

Building on this, the general idea of Christianity is that God (Love), an abstract concept, decided to incarnate in the flesh and live among us, thereby redeeming humanity as beings capable of eternal life, because Love itself is eternal. Therefore, I just cannot find myself agreeing with any point of view that paints hell as a form of punishment.

There is no fear in love, but perfect love casts out fear. For fear has to do with punishment, and whoever fears has not been perfected in love. **1 John 4:18**

3.3.1 The Problem of Pain

There is so much suffering and strife in the world, and it is hard, really hard to keep believing in love, but I am comforted by my deep conviction that eventually, we will all learn to love just as God intends.

The Lord is not slow to fulfill His promise as some count slowness, but is patient toward you, not wishing that any should perish, but that **all** should reach repentance. **2 Peter 3:9**

The way I see things, if we truly believe God to be omnipotent (all-powerful), omnipresent (ever-present), and omniscient (all-knowing), it is simply impossible for human free will to override His wishes!

So that at the name of Jesus every knee should bow, in heaven and on earth and under the earth, and every tongue confess that Jesus Christ is Lord, to the glory of God the Father. **Philippians 2:10–11**

My life has been a journey of near-misses and “coincidences”, which I now attribute solely to God’s Grace. When I think of how many split-second decisions “I” have made that completely altered the course of my life, I just feel nothing but wonder for being a pencil in the hand of the Creator as He writes His story (shout-out to Wale Adenuga and the Nigerian TV Drama, *Super Story*).

That said, I recognize that I can say this because I am privileged and happy with where I am today. There are millions in pain who want to believe like I do, but do not have physical, mental, or emotional reason to. And then we ask, does God create pain? Is pain and suffering necessary for God’s plan to be carried out? My answer is no. The Bible itself also mentions that pain does not have to happen, and to even suggest that God needs evil to carry out his eternal plan of Love is a faulty line of thinking.

And why not do evil that good may come? - as some people slanderously charge us with saying. Their condemnation is just. **Romans 3:8**

I do not feel qualified to address exactly why bad things happen in this world, but I *am* committed to using my life to spread goodness. That said, I also believe that God, whose name is Love, can re-purpose any pain for goodness. In the Bible, Joseph was beaten and sold into slavery by his brothers, which I clearly believe is evil. Yet, Joseph ended up as the de-facto ruler of Egypt in the end. So I want to encourage anyone going through a hard time to never stop believing in love as they work to get out of their bad situation, because Love Will Find A Way (LWFAW).

3.3.2 The Birth of Consciousness

In several religions, from Christianity to Islam to the Epic of Gilgamesh, a story similar to Adam and Eve exists. Basically, the idea is that humanity was created and placed in paradise, or the “Garden of Eden”, but

disobediently ate a fruit that awakened our self-awareness (whether this was a literal or allegorical “fruit” is beside the point, in my opinion). It was called the fruit of the “tree of knowledge of good and evil”, or in other words, *knowledge of something other than love*.

The first non-loving emotion humanity was shown to experience is shame:

shame

/SHām/

a painful feeling of humiliation or distress caused by the **consciousness** of wrong or foolish behavior.

Unlike, say, a horse, which will readily empty its bowels in your living room if it ends up there for whatever reason, we are now conscious of how our actions affect others. Farting in public is considered impolite not because it is wrong to let the gas out, but because we are *aware* that it provides an unpleasant experience for those who are unfortunate enough to inhale the fumes, LOL. And even then, if our goal changed (channeling Adler here), and we somehow wanted to achieve the goal of making the room as smelly as possible, suddenly, farting becomes a good thing - the event remained the same (farting), but our perception of it changed due to a change in our goal. Therefore, wouldn't things be a lot better if everyone's goal was love?

And He said to him, “You shall love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind. This is the great and first commandment. And a second is like it: You shall love your neighbor as yourself.”

Matthew 22:37–39

I think everyone has that innate desire to love, but our limited consciousness is getting in the way of that. I called our consciousness limited because we would need to be omniscient to fully understand the butterfly effect of everything we do - which we are not.

“God understands the way to it and he alone knows where it dwells, for he views the ends of the earth and sees everything under the heavens.”

Job 28:23–24

So if we all want to love each other, why is our consciousness, or ego, getting in the way of that? What purpose does it serve that makes it hard to let go?

3.3.3 Love vs Control

Your kingdom come, Your will be done, on earth as it is in heaven.

Matthew 6:10

In the previous section, I suggested that our consciousness is getting in the way of our ability to love perfectly. A world where everyone loves each other regardless of race, gender, or any other external quality would be heaven, wouldn't it? So what is getting in the way of achieving heaven on earth?

Figure 9: Cover art for the single *Let's Go Crazy* (Warner Bros. Records, 1984)

Do you know this song? It's one of my favorites. In the opening monologue, Prince describes "heaven" like this:

*There's something else
The afterworld
A world of never-ending happiness
You can always see the sun, day or night*

I had to pause for a bit to think about why we always describe paradise in these terms. We say heaven is paved with "streets of gold". Gold, which is an incredibly scarce resource on earth. In the Prince quote above, heaven is described as an existence where things we usually consider "good" (happiness, sunlight, etc.) are infinitely available. And that's when it clicked - LOVE IS ABUNDANCE.

Here's a thought experiment, let's think about something that makes you annoyed, no matter how great or little. Actually, to really illustrate this point, let's go for a minor inconvenience like accidentally slamming the door on your coat as you're rushing to work. Where does the irritation come from? I argue that it's because of scarcity. Scarcity of time - you've just wasted some time, a finite resource, because something didn't go as you expected it to. The annoyance could also stem from a scarcity of resources - the coat is something that costs money, and slamming the door on it reduces its utility (roughens it, rips the fabric, etc).

I have repeated this thought experiment several times on several scenarios, and I arrive at the same conclusion each time - I believe that every evil that has been committed in this world is as a result of scarcity, with the scale varying with the crime. In essence, *scarcity brings in us a need to **control** outcomes*, because leaving things up to fate has a cost. And on this note, I think control is a survival mechanism - it is the cost of living in a finite world. It protects us. Scarcity of land is the reason private property exists, but the seemingly infinite nature of air is the reason nobody needs to control or ration it (at least right now, because with the level of environmental pollution going on we might get to a point where we need to do that). On the flip side, we can equally see the connection between love and abundance. In 1 Corinthians 13:4-8, scripture says love is kind (generosity, care, etc. come from an abundance of physical and emotional resources), love is patient (patience comes from an abundance of time), and so on.

Therefore, doesn't it make sense to focus our technological efforts on creating a post-scarcity society so we can all love better?

3.3.4 The Purpose of our Existence

The Lord God took the man and put him in the garden of Eden to work it and keep it. **Genesis 2:15**

I believe that our original purpose, as beings of higher intelligence on earth, was to steward creation (*keep it*), and co-create with God (*work it*). In love. This point of view is further supported by Jesus' parable of the talents:

A master, before going on a journey, entrusts his servants with different amounts of money ("talents").

One receives 5 talents, another 2 talents, and another gets 1 talent.

The first two servants invest what they've been given and double it. The master praises them, saying:

"Well done, good and faithful servant... You have been faithful with a few things; I will put you in charge of many things. Come and share your master's happiness!" (Matthew 25:21, 23).

But the third servant, afraid of losing the money, hides his talent and returns only what was given. The master rebukes him:

"You wicked, lazy servant!"

He loses even the little he was given, and is cast out.

Although "talents" here referred to money (i.e, 1 talent was equivalent 6,000 drachmas or denarii, the Greek and Roman silver coins), I see this as our innate abilities. Every person was born with different gifts and abilities, and our life's purpose is to use those gifts to create things in love, which includes creating a society that can enable others to use their talents as well. Speaking for myself, I am autistic, and while it is

considered a “disability”, my autism is the reason I am able to recognize patterns and make the connections between my different interests as I am doing in this work. However, not all autistic people have low support needs like me, and I think it is up to those of us with privilege to make the world more inclusive and equal so that everyone can have a chance to fulfill their God-given purpose.

Just as each servant in the parable was given a different amount of talents, I believe everyone is given a unique skillset, which translates to a unique purpose. That said, based on everything I have written up to this point, I hope you will agree with me that each and every one of our talents was intended to serve one ultimate goal - love.

3.3.5 Hell as a Refiner’s Fire

With everything set up, this section will attempt to describe Hell as an act of love, as a form of restoration. This view of hell forms the basis of my understanding of Christian Universalism. My favorite verse that illustrates this view is in the first letter Paul wrote to the Corinthian church:

“If anyone builds on this foundation using gold, silver, costly stones, wood, hay or straw, their work will be shown for what it is, because the Day will bring it to light. It will be revealed with fire, and the fire will test the quality of each person’s work. If what has been built survives, the builder will receive a reward. If it is burned up, **the builder will suffer loss but yet will be saved - even though only as one escaping through the flames.**” **1 Corinthians 3:12–15**

As mentioned earlier, we were born to create. We are the builders, and our lives are meant to be never-ending streams of creation - with creations made for the purpose of love being the only things we carry into eternity. Why do you think we write “In *Loving* Memory” on tombstones? What is life other than a chance to consciously create more loving memories even with the knowledge of the alternative??

In this way, viewing Hell through the lens of God’s nature (i.e Love), it is a “refiner’s fire”, a way to burn up the parts of us incompatible with love. Much earlier in this work we discussed how we construct our belief systems about ourselves in relation to the world around us as we go through life (also a form of creation). And I think hell is a “fire” (again, whether it is a literal fire or a metaphor is besides the point) that burns up those parts of us that were not created from a place of love, because love is the only thing that is eternal!!!!

I see Hell as passing through TSA. Our lives are the time we spend packing for the trip to eternity, which is Love. The times we spend creating love even with the presence/knowledge of *something other than love*. And when we get to the checkpoint, the officer will ask a simple question:

Can you open your bag for me?

If it's full of Hawaiian T-Shirts and flipflops, the officer might joke with you about how much fun you're about to have. However, if you have a pound of cocaine in your bag, you're obviously gonna start sweating, weeping and gnashing your teeth (Matthew 25:30) and wasting everyone's time. Refusing to open the bag for as long as you can (a la C.S. Lewis' famous "*the gates of hell are locked from the inside*"). But at some point you're going to have to open it, and the drugs you wanted to smuggle will be destroyed and suffer the "punishment" of eternal fire (Jude 1:7). For *aiōnios*. That is, just as Love is eternal, anything incompatible with Love will be destroyed forever. You (made in the image of God) and rest of your luggage (things you constructed/created during your lifetime) will still make it through, though, just as long as it is compatible with Love!

3.3.6 Scriptural Support for the Redemptive Nature of Hell

To support the previous section, I'd like to provide a bit more scriptural support for the redemptive, restorative nature of "hell".

These two are pretty good:

"But who can endure the day of his coming? Who can stand when he appears? For he will be like a refiner's fire or a launderer's soap. He will sit as a refiner and purifier of silver; he will purify the Levites and refine them like gold and silver. Then the Lord will have men who will bring offerings in righteousness."

Malachi 3:2–3

"This third I will put into the fire; I will refine them like silver and test them like gold. They will call on my name and I will answer them; I will say, 'They are my people,' and they will say, 'The Lord is our God.'"

Zechariah 13:9

They clearly emphasize how hell is refinement of the "self" which contains eternal essence (i.e., "*Imago Dei*", or the image of God) and flawed constructs. Let's look at a few more places in scripture that can be interpreted through a universalist lens.

Moses and the Burning Bush

Moses was one of the central prophetic figures in the Old Testament, considered to have spoken to Love face to face, as one speaks to a friend (Exodus 33:11). However, he wasn't always like that. The first time he met God, he was in a land called Midian, which he fled to after killing an Egyptian. While tending to his father-in-law's livestock, flames of fire appeared from within a bush. **Yet, although the bush was on**

fire, it did not burn up!

When Moses went closer to take a look, Love (God) told him to stop, because he was on **“holy ground”**!! That is, the bush did not burn up because there were no “flawed constructs” to refine!

I want to stress that I am not saying that any particular patch of land in modern day Arabia (where Midian was) is holy. Just to be clear haha.

Wheat and Chaff

Here is an image of wheat and chaff (wheat on the right, chaff on the left).

Figure 10: Wheat and Chaff

Yet, both grow **from the same plant!!!**

Figure 11: Shameless Self-Promotion

Now, for the scripture that demonstrates the refining nature of God's judgement:

“I baptize you with water for repentance. But after me comes one who is more powerful than I, whose sandals I am not worthy to carry. He will baptize you with the Holy Spirit and fire. His winnowing fork is in his hand, and he will clear his threshing floor, gathering his wheat into the barn and burning up the chaff with unquenchable fire.” **Matthew 3:11–12**

A similar analogy, the parable of the net, is used by Jesus to explain:

“Once again, the kingdom of heaven is like a net that was let down into the lake and caught all kinds of fish. When it was full, the fishermen pulled it up on the shore. Then they sat down and collected the good fish in baskets, but threw the bad away. This is how it will be at the end of the age. The angels will come and separate the wicked from the righteous and throw them into the blazing furnace, where there will be weeping and gnashing of teeth.” **Matthew 13:47–50**

While I concede that this one seems more like the fish refers to the person, I am proposing here that the net is actually the person! That is, the “bad fish” are the identity constructs that are incompatible with love! **I just think it had to be explained this way (see Matthew 13:36–43 for Jesus' explanation) because ancient Jewish people probably couldn't have comprehended the concept of the “self” (constructivism as a theory didn't come up until the late 19th century/early 20th century)!!!** Of course, this interpretation may stretch the original metaphor, but I strongly believe its spirit aligns with the holistic vision of Love the Gospel presents.

In summary, I think the question to ask is not whether we are “saved” or not. Instead, I think it makes more sense to ask whether we want to arrive at eternity barely knowing how to walk, or prepared to run an ultra-marathon - that is, how much would we have developed the ability to love by the end of our lives? Christ Himself has made it clear that salvation is an ongoing process.

Then he said to them all: “Whoever wants to be my disciple must deny themselves and take up their cross **daily** and follow me.” **Luke 9:23**

3.3.7 How to Love

I have realized recently how far I am from knowing how to love. Over the course of my life, I have constructed a lot of faulty beliefs about the nature of love, which I have been working hard to unlearn. For example, I am still working hard to learn the difference between admiration/attention and love. They sometimes look and feel the same, but are soooo different. Remember, Jesus triumphantly rode into Jerusalem to the praise of everyone on Sunday, and was crucified by the same people five days later LOL.

I think one of the best practices I use is to say this verse out loud (or in my head):

Love is patient, love is kind. It does not envy, it does not boast, it is not proud. It does not dishonor others, it is not self-seeking, it is not easily angered, it keeps no record of wrongs. Love does not delight in evil but rejoices with the truth. It always protects, always trusts, always hopes, always perseveres. Love never fails.

1 Corinthians 13:4–8

replacing “Love” with “I”. That is, “*I am patient, I am kind...*” and then being honest with myself about whether what I am saying is actually true LMAO. Of course, to completely live like this all the time is basically impossible, as that’d mean I’m perfect, which I’m not. Nonetheless, saying these “affirmations” out loud are a reminder to at least *try*.

4 Restorative Practice

Figure 12: Gustavo Fring of *Los Pollos Hermanos* (Breaking Bad TV Show)

I do not believe fear to be an effective motivator.

Gustavo Fring

Restorative Practice is an alternative legal and social paradigm that focuses on repairing relationships and promoting healing, as opposed to using fear and punishment. As discussed extensively in the previous section, restoration is the true nature of Love's Justice, and I added a slight modification to Adlerian Psychology (which is proven to work) to argue that we are all innately motivated by love. In this section I will share a few areas where restorative practice can (and has) been applied.

4.1 Lessons from Material Science: Lenard-Jones Interatomic Potential

One of the tools I use in my research is a simulation method called “Molecular Dynamics”, where we try to simulate how things behave down to the atoms. To do so, we have to come up with an equation that describes how the atoms interact with each other. One of the most universal descriptions of how atoms behave is called the “Lenard Jones Potential”.

Figure 13: Lenard-Jones Interatomic Potential

Basically, it describes how atoms that make up a material will naturally try to arrange themselves. In summary, it says that every two atoms that try to interact will always try to use the least amount of energy possible. Not zero energy, some energy is still used. They just try to use as little energy as possible to maintain balance/equilibrium.

In the context of Restorative Practice, we can take a lesson from nature and create systems that make doing the “right thing” cost the least amount of energy.

That said, every person is unique, as we discussed earlier in the parable of the talents, which means everyone has their own unique “Lenard-Jones Potential” for interacting with different people.

Figure 14: Different LJ Potentials

I think creating a society that accounts for these differences can help us love better. To close everything out, I'll discuss a few examples of restorative practice.

4.2 Practical Applications

4.2.1 Environmental Systems

During the COVID-19 lockdowns, nature rebounded rapidly - not because new resources were introduced, but because human interference was temporarily removed. The Earth returned toward equilibrium and we saw photos of clear skies, animals returning, and waters clearing. I think these were the natural result of a lower-energy, less-extractive/exploitative system. When a system is no longer forced out of balance, it finds rest and repair on its own.

4.2.2 Piracy and Streaming

Downloading music from sites like mp3skull was once the least-energy path to listening to music, and piracy flourished. When streaming services made access simpler (lower energy), piracy declined - not through punishment, but through better system design (whether streaming is “better” for artists is debatable, but that’s a topic for another day).

4.2.3 Personal Relationships: “Equally Yoked”

A healthy relationship mirrors the Lennard-Jones model: too much closeness leads to codependence and burnout, but too much distance breeds disconnection.

Every person has a unique bonding energy, that is, an optimal amount of closeness/distance they need to feel secure, seen, and free. A healthy relationship (platonic, romantic, familial, professional, etc.) is one where a good balance is struck.

4.2.4 Legal Systems/Restorative Justice

Punishment is a high-energy system - it isolates, stigmatizes, and often breeds resentment, which leads to even more anti-social behavior. Restorative practice in this context aims to reintegrate, humanize, and reestablish healthy proximity.

One effort that has demonstrated the effectiveness of this is the Northwestern Prison Education Program (NPEP) which I have gotten a chance to be involved with (this is also where I learned about restorative justice for the first time!).

Studies show that tackling complex, communal, idea-driven tasks (like graduate-level education) correlates with near-zero recidivism [7]. I think this is because it helps incarcerated people see how their innate goals of belonging, purpose, and ultimately, love, can be met through healthier channels that cost less energy than crime (while also helping them fully understand the effects of their actions on the community in general).

5 Conclusion

I'd make some grand academic conclusion here but I feel like I already made my point lol. Thanks for reading!!!! I love you all!!!

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